

A NEW BIODEGRADABLE BIOPLASTIC TERNARY BLEND AS NEW MATRIX SYSTEM FOR BIOCOMPOSITE USES

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1 Introduction

Recently, advanced polymeric materials from biopolymers derived from natural resources have attracted great interest due to the growing concern over environmental issues and limited petroleum resources. Especially in recent years, great efforts have been made in developing high performance bioplastic based blends and composites from renewable resources for use in applications for commercial product [1, 2]. One of the most promising and important research areas is developing biocomposites from bioplastic and nature fiber [1]. Combined biopolymer with low cost nature fiber provide us new eco-friendly materials with attractive benefits such as biodegradability, value-added for natural products, high modulus and light weight, which exhibits a prospect of much wider application such as automotive parts and electronic products [1].

In this regards, biodegradable plastics such as polyhydroxyalkanoates (PHAs), polylactide (PLA), and poly (butylene succinate) (PBS) produced from renewable resources are really appealing choice as a matrix for the biocomposites. As a most important biopolymer, PLA has been intensively investigated and used in biomedical application area due to its excellent biocompatibility and biodegradability [3, 4]. In recent years, its full bio-renewability, commercial availability, and decreasing cost have attracted intensive scientific and industrial interest to expand its application in wide range of products.

PLA possesses excellent stiffness and processability, which makes it a promising matrix for structural biocomposites application. However, neat PLA showed poor flexibility with an elongation only at about 4%. [3-4] Moreover, the low crystallinity results in poor heat resistance at high temperature. The inherent brittleness and poor thermal resistance

of PLA significantly limits its wide potential application. To overcome the deficiency of PLA, extensive efforts have been performed including copolymerization, plasticization and physical blending. Copolymerization is a powerful approach to enhance the toughness and flexibility of PLA. However, most of the synthesized process needs expensive reagents, complicated steps and strict synthesis conditions, which are difficult and not suitable for industrial production [5]. Plasticization by blending with low molecular weight plasticizers is another widely used way. But, the occurred plasticizer aging during the long term use time is a greatly defect for this method [4-5]. Compared to chemical modification method, physical blending is more cost-effective way to modify the performance of the components. PLA has been blended with lot of flexible polymers such as poly (ϵ -caprolactone) and poly (butylene adipate-co-terephthalate), etc. [4, 5] However, most of the work focused on the binary blend. In the binary blend, usually, the strength and stiffness of PLA were satisfied during the toughening of the PLA.

Poly(3-hydroxybutyrate-co-3-hydroxyvalerate) (PHBV) is another very promising biodegradable polymer derived from renewable resource with good thermal properties and comparable mechanical strength and modulus [2]. As well-known polymers produced directly by bacterial fermentation from renewable sources, PHBV possesses more excellent resistances to water, gas and high temperature of PHBV compared to other biodegradable polyesters. This unique property makes it an ideal choice to replace petroleum based plastic in using at high temperature. Nevertheless, commercial use of PHBV is highly hindered by its high cost, narrow processing temperatures, poor flexibility and toughness.

Flexibility and toughness are highly required performance for many applications at low temperatures. Among the biodegradable polyesters, PBS shows excellent flexibility with high elongation up to 300% at low temperatures. Nowadays, succinic acid and 1, 4 butandiol, the monomers used to synthesize PBS, can be produced from natural resources such as starch and oligosaccharides. This technological progress makes it possible to have reducing the dependence on petroleum resources [6]. Despite its advantages, the low strength and thermal properties of PBS also cannot fulfill the requirement for many structural applications.

As pointed out above, when used alone, none of PLA, PHBV and PBS can satisfy the requirement for the several structural and/or semi-structural biocomposites uses. The inherent deficiencies of these polymers have significantly hindered their applications as matrix for biomass fibers. The recent development of bioplastics has created a new trend in using bioplastic multiphase blends unlike individual bioplastic as matrix system for biocomposite applications. Multiphase polymeric materials including polymer blends and composites have drawn intense commercial interest due to the attractive combined properties, competitive cost and processing advantages [7-10]. A lot of efforts have been focused on developing multiphase materials from petroleum-based materials such as polypropylene (PP), polyethylene (PE) and polystyrene (PS) [7-9]. It has been approved that multiphase polymer blends is one of the most promising and inexpensive ways of obtaining new desirable combinations of properties to satisfy the increasing application requirement [8]. However, to best of our knowledge, only limited efforts have concentrated on the multiphase polymer materials from bioplastic from renewable resources [10]. Recently, we have reported the biorenewable and biodegradable ternary blend of PLA, PHBV and PBS to achieve a novel biopolymer matrix with balanced properties [3]. Our results suggested that multiphase polymeric blends is a promising way to obtain bioplastic matrix with appropriated thermal properties, stiffness-toughness balanced performance and processing properties.

In this work, based on the previous research, we further studied the new formulation of PLA/PHBV/PBS blend to achieve desired properties. Two new formulation of

PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10) and PLA/PHBV/PBS (20/60/20) were fabricated to achieve balanced mechanical and thermal performance. The mechanical properties were studied systematically and compared with neat PLA and PHBV.

2 Materials, Methods and Characterization

The PLA used in the present work was bought from NatureWorks (USA). It is a injection-grade (PLA 3251D) with a M_w of 5.5×10^4 g/cm³ and polydispersity index (PI) of 1.62. The PHBV (Mirel P1004, a product from Telles In.) is obtained from Competitive Green Technologies, ON, Canada. PBS, with trade name of Bionolle 1020, was procured from Toyo Plastics Co., Ltd, Japan, which is a product of Showa Highpolymer Co. Ltd, Japan

Before blending, all the samples were dried at 80°C for at least 4 h in a conventional oven to get rid of the moisture. Blends of varying compositions were melt-processed by a micro-compounder (DSM-Xplore, Netherlands). The length and L/D of the screws are of 150 mm and 18, respectively. The barrel volume of the machine is 15 cm³. The extrusion was performed at barrel temperature of 180 °C in a screw speed at 100 rpm. After processed for 2.5 min, a preheated cylinder was used to transfer the molten blend material to a preheated injection molder to prepare various test specimens. At the same time, the neat PLA and PHBV were also processed under the same condition to obtain the same thermal history.

Tensile and flexural tests were performed on Instron universal testing machine (model 3382) at room temperature. The tensile and flexural test is performed according to ASTM standards D638 and D790, respectively. At least five samples were measured for each category.

The Izod impact strength was measured by a Testing Machine Inc. (TMI) instrument according to ASTM D256. At least five notched samples were measured for each category.

The morphology of the typical fracture surfaces obtained from impact test was observed by Hitachi S-570 scanning electron microscope (SEM). The samples were sputtered by gold before the test.

3 Results and Discussion

3.1 Tensile properties

Tensile properties of the neat PLA, PHBV and polymer ternary blends were firstly studied. Figure 1 presented the tensile strength and modulus properties of neat PLA, PHBV and the ternary blends. The elongation was shown in Figure 2. As shown in the figures, neat PLA showed highest strength and modulus indicating its high stiffness. However, its elongation at break is only at 3.8%. For the neat PHBV, the elongation at break is slightly higher than that of PLA with a value up to 10%. However, its strength and modulus is lower than those of PLA. The poor flexibility of PLA and PHBV are the main bottlenecks which significantly hinder their application in biocomposites and other potential applications.

Blending with other flexible polymer is an widely used method to modify the flexibility of PLA and PHBV [4, 5]. When flexible PBS was added in the ternary blend, one can note in Figure 2 that the elongation at break of the blend was significantly improved compared to neat components. Especially for the blend PLA/PHBV/PBS (20/60/20), the elongation increased up to 72%, seven times higher than neat PHBV and almost 20 times higher than PLA. During the test, stable neck growth and obvious yield point were observed for the blend samples. This clearly suggested that a ductile fracture occurs during the tensile test. Toughening of a brittle polymer occurs usually at the cost of its strength in binary blends [3, 4]. Compared to neat PLA, the stiffness of the blend was decreased due to the addition of soft PHBV and PBS phases. However, compared to neat PHBV, one can note that improvement in both the stiffness and flexibility were observed. This unique phenomenon can be explained by synergistic action performed by PBS and PLA phases. For PHBV in the multiphase system, the stiff PLA phase reinforced the strength and modulus, whereas the soft PBS phases improved the flexibility. An interesting combination of properties was achieved owing to the interplay of these phases in the ternary blend, which is unable to be achieved in the normal binary systems [3].

3.2 Impact strength

Figure 3 presented the impact properties of the ternary blends and neat polymers. As a typical brittle

polymer, PLA showed only impact strength of 17 J/m and the samples broke in brittle manners. All the blends clearly showed higher toughness than neat PLA and PHBV. The impact strength for the blends was increased nearly to double times higher than that of neat PLA. However, compared to neat PHBV, the improvement in impact strength is not so obvious compared with the drastic improvement in elongation observed for the PHBV based blend. During the impact or tensile test, stress concentration occurred at the interface of the separated phases due to the interfacial cavitations and the different elastic property. The stress concentration initiated shear deformation of the phases, which is a high-energy-absorbing mechanism [3]. Followed the matrix yielding, the stress was then transferred to the soft PHBV and PBS phases. Then to release the energy, the orientation of separated domains formed during the process. The corresponding amount of plastic deformation effectively improved the toughness by dissipating the energy. However, for PLA minor phase in the blend PLA/PHBV/PBS (20/60/20), its high stiffness inhibited its deformation under the test. Consequently, the improvement of the toughness of the blend with PHBV as matrix was not so evident.

Figure 4 showed the typical morphology of fracture surface of neat components and the PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10) blend. One can clearly noted that neat PLA showed typical brittle fracture manners. smooth surface without apparent matrix yielding was observed. Neat PHBV showed better toughness compared to PLA. In order to figure out the role of different phases during the fracture process, high magnification was adopted for the PLA/PBV/PBS (45/45/10) blend.

For the blend PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10), it was found that the surface was rougher than neat PLA, which also indicated that the matrix yield during the test. Although it was difficult to clearly distinguish the different phases due to the yield deformation, some ovals cavities were still visible. This may be attributed to the deboning occurred at the interface near the different phases. Moreover, the matrix deformation around the cavity was also observed which resulted in a favorable toughening effect [4]. The morphology of the fracture surface confirmed the above mechanism to some extent. This

mechanism also was applied to the tensile test process.

3.3 Flexural properties

The pursuit of the balance of strength and toughness is a key target in polymer blend. Unfortunately, these properties are of conflict during a melt blending in usual [3]. Flexural characterization can directly provide the information of the stiffness of the materials. Figure 5 showed the flexural properties of the samples. Neat PLA showed highest flexural strength with a value up to 114 MPa and flexural modulus up to 3.8 GPa. However, the flexural modulus of PHBV is just at 1.5 GPa indicating the relatively poor stiffness compared with PLA. All the blends showed the strength and modulus values at intermediate of the neat PLA and PHBV. The blend with 45 wt% PLA showed higher modulus and strength than the blend with only 20 wt% PLA added. The strength and modulus decreased with the content of PLA decreasing, which suggested that the stiff PLA phases play an positive role in enhancing the strength of the blends. The decreased stiffness in the blend was mainly attributed to the addition of soft PBS. The more content of PBS added, more dramatic decrease in strength occurred. Consequently, optimizing the formulation of the three components in the ternary blend is one of key point to achieve the balanced performance. This is also true for other properties such as thermal resistance.

4 Conclusion

In the present work, we fabricated PLA/PHBV/PBS ternary blend to obtain novel bioplastic matrix for natural fiber biocomposites. Our results indicated that multiphases system of PLA, PHBV and PBS provided us a simple and effective way to develop a new matrix system for biomass fiber. Compared to neat components, the ternary blends of PLA/PHBV/PBS showed good balanced mechanical properties. Especially for the PHBV based blend, a unique stiffness-toughness balance achieved due to the positive combination effect of PLA and PBS phases. Although the PBS used in present work is not biobased polymer, the developing of biobased PBS from renewable sources has made substantial

progress recently. The inherent biorenewable characteristic and full biodegradability makes this PLA/PHBV/PBS multiphases system a very promising alternative to petroleum plastic for the biocomposites application. The other properties of the mutiphases system are under investigation. The biocomposites based on the multiphase bioplastic system are also under progress.

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Fig. 2. Elongation of PLA/PHBV/PBS ternary blends: (A) Neat PLA; (B) Neat PHBV; (C) PLA/PHBV/PBS 45/45/10; (D) PLA/PHBV/PBS 20/60/20.

Fig. 1. Young's modulus and tensile strength of PLA/PHBV/PBS ternary blends: (A) Neat PLA; (B) Neat PHBV; (C) PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10); (D) PLA/PHBV/PBS (20/60/20).

Fig. 3. Notched Izod impact strength of PLA/PHBV/PBS ternary blends: (A) Neat PLA; (B) Neat PHBV; (C) PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10); (D) PLA/PHBV/PBS (20/60/20).

(A)

(C)

(B)

Fig. 4: SEM morphology of typical impact surface of (A) neat PLA, (B) neat PHBV, (C) PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10).

Fig. 5. Flexural modulus and strength of PLA/PHBV/PBS ternary blends: (A) Neat PLA; (B) Neat PHBV; (C) PLA/PHBV/PBS (45/45/10); (D) PLA/PHBV/PBS (20/60/20).